

ISic0653

I.Sicily inscription 0653

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Taormina, Antiquarium del
Teatro Antico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332973

1. πάντων [ἦν μὲν(?)]
2. ἐγὼ φίλος [ἐκ προγο]-
3. νῶν παῖς [ἐσθλῶν] |
4. χρηστότητ [α □ - κεῖμαι]
5. νῦν ἐνθάδε [(nomen)].
- 6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644893

PHI 332973

Bibliography

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